
From Data to Innovation

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Abstract: Data can be the source of innovation. Data can help to analyse the constitution of the people involved in the innovation process and to give them recommendations along the innovation process to increase their innovation performance, productivity in individual and group work and to optimise the quality of the results. The article proposes a long-term study in which the innovation potential of young adults in secondary schools, universities and companies is continuously recorded. The aim is to develop a chatbot that supports individuals in transforming their innovation potential into innovation performance, so that innovations develop that transform society. The aim is to improve the quality of innovation outcomes and the productivity of individuals involved in solving complex problems.

Keywords: Innovation, Achievement, Potential, Data-based Decisioning.

1 Introduction

Gifted adults as a source of innovation

Innovation is a top priority in Germany.^{1 2 3} Innovation is the result of people working together along the innovation process to produce innovations.^{4 5 6} Science has shown in various studies that gifted or talented people are better at solving complex problems.^{7 8}

¹ ZEW, "Wie steht es um die Innovationsfähigkeit Deutschlands?," Online Article (ZEW – Leibniz Centre for European Economic Research, directed by Hanna Hottenrott et al.), 2024, <https://www.zew.de/en/publications/wie-steht-es-um-die-innovationsfaehigkeit-deutschlands-1>, accessed April 2024.

² Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung, "Scholz schlägt Deutschlandpakt vor," Online Article (FAZ.NET, directed by Gerald Braunberger et al.), 2022, <https://www.faz.net/aktuell/politik/scholz-schlaegt-deutschlandpakt-vor-19155568.html>, accessed April 2024.

³ EFI, "Report 2023," Online Article (EFI – Commission of Experts for Research and Innovation, directed by Prof. Dr. Uwe Cantner), 2023, https://www.e-fi.de/fileadmin/Assets/Gutachten/2023/EFI_Report_2023.pdf, accessed April 2024.

⁴ David Yun Dai, "How advances in gifted education contribute to innovation education, and vice versa," *The Routledge International Handbook of Innovation Education* (2013): 82-97.

⁵ Teresa M. Amabile, "A model of creativity and innovation in organizations," *Research in Organizational Behavior* 10.1 (1988): 123-167.

⁶ Mel, Rhodes, "An analysis of creativity," *The Phi delta kappan* 42.7 (1961): 305-310.

⁷ Norbert Jaušovec, "Differences in cognitive processes between gifted, intelligent, creative, and average individuals while solving complex problems: An EEG study," *Intelligence* 28.3 (2000): 213-237.

⁸ Jonathan Wai and Benjamin J. Lovett, "Improving gifted talent development can help solve multiple consequential real-world problems," *Journal of Intelligence* 9.2 (2021): 31.

Throughout the innovation process, people solve complex problems co-creatively.⁹ ¹⁰ Ideally innovations that are created in the here and now are sustainable or circular.¹¹

Research suggests that gifted adults are particularly capable of innovation, with their abilities being shaped by a combination of well above average ability, task commitment, and creativity.¹² However, the development of innovation skills in the gifted population is often neglected, with a need for more comprehensive education interventions.¹³ ¹⁴ The potential for innovation in gifted individuals is further supported by the observation that young people possess traits of successful innovators.¹⁵ The correlation between creativity and intelligence, while positive, is only moderate, suggesting that creativity extends beyond intelligence.¹⁶ Therefore, nurturing the talents of the gifted population is crucial for societal innovation.¹¹

How do we know if learners have the potential to become innovators?

Several studies have highlighted the need for better talent identification and management in Germany. Landwehr¹⁷ found that many organizations need more effective talent management practices, while Urban¹⁸ identified a need for more attention to the needs of gifted children. Almeida¹⁹ and Zinner²⁰ highlighted the problem of unrecognized talent in schools. Prinz²¹ and Peter²² emphasized the need for improved talent identification and management across sectors. These studies suggest that many people in Germany may need to be made aware of their talents due to a lack of recognition and support.

Fischer²³ emphasizes the growing importance of supporting gifted children. Various organizations and institutions offer measures such as scholarships, special academies, and

⁹ Alfred Shiu-ho Wong and Dean Tjosvold, "Innovating across cultural boundaries: applying conflict theory to develop a common approach," *International Negotiation* 9 (2004): 291-313.

¹⁰ P. Mattila, B. Eisenbart, A. Kocsis, C. Ranscombe, and T. Tuulos, "Transformation is a game we can't play alone: Diversity and co-creation as key to thriving innovation ecosystems," In *Research into Design for a Connected World*, eds. Amaresh Chakrabarti (Springer Singapore, 2019), p. 151-162.

¹¹ Sabrina Schork, "Circular Innovator Education," In *Ability*, eds. Erwin Sengers (Ode to the Seekers, 2021), p. 105-124.

¹² Joseph S. Renzulli, "The Three-Ring Conception of Giftedness: Its Implications for Understanding the Nature of Innovation," In *Handbook on Innovation*, eds. Larisa V. Shavinina (Elsevier Science, 2003), p. 79-96.

¹³ Larisa V. Shavinina, "How to develop innovators? Innovation education for the gifted," *Gifted Education International* 29 (2013): 54 - 68.

¹⁴ Joyce Vantassel-Baska, "Creativity and Innovation," In *Giftedness and Talent in the 21st Century*, eds. D. Ambrose and R. J. Sternberg (Sense Publishers, 2016), p. 221-233.

¹⁵ Ilona Dougherty and Amelia Clarke, "Wired for Innovation," *Emerging Adulthood* 6 (2018): 358-365.

¹⁶ Julian C. Stanley, "The riddle of creativity," *Peabody Journal of Education* 34 (1956): 78-81.

¹⁷ Jens Landwehr, "The use of talent management instruments and procedures in Germany: A broad explorative study of effectiveness and success factors," *Journal of Human Resource Management* 4.6 (2016): 77-99.

¹⁸ Klaus K. Urban "Hochbegabte Kinder-eine Herausforderung," *Bildung und Erziehung* 33. Jg (1980): 526-535.

¹⁹ Maria Amélia Almeida and Vera Lúcia Capellini, "Alunos talentosos: possíveis superdotados não notados," *Educação* 28.1 (2005): 45-64.

²⁰ J. Zinner, C. Werner, S. Mehler, and L. M. Abraldes Rois, „Berlin hat Talent 'Ergebnisse der Untersuchungen in mehreren Bezirken von Berlin 2014',“ *Zeitschrift für Gesundheit und Sport* 5.1 (2015): 1-14.

²¹ Birgit Prinz and Peter Wollsching-Strobel, "Verschenkte Talente—oder die Misere mangelnder Talenterkennung und-förderung," *Talentmanagement mit System: Von Top-Performern lernen-Leistungsträger im Unternehmen wirksam unterstützen Der PWS-Ansatz* (2012): 3-23.

²² Tobias Peter, "Talent. Zu einem Schlüsselbegriff zeitgenössischer Bildung," *Begabung und Gesellschaft: Sozialwissenschaftliche Perspektiven auf Begabung und Begabtenförderung* (2018): 71-93.

²³ Christian Fischer and Kerstin Mätzler, "Gifted education and talent support in Germany," *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal* 4.3 (2014): 31-54.

competitions. However, a comprehensive strategy needs to be improved, with individual countries offering their activities.

How can we establish education focusing on innovation and the gifted?

The World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs 2023 study shows that companies primarily seek creative, analytical, and deep data/AI skills.²⁴ These skills are highly relevant for innovators. Innovators need various skills such as problem-solving, collaboration, agility, initiative, written and verbal skills, assessment, analysis, curiosity, and imagination.²⁵ A scientific approach, research skills, and a deep understanding of the profession are also crucial.²⁶ Innovative thinking, which involves different, divergent, and shifting thinking, is the foundation of a leader's ability to innovate.²⁷ However, the current mechanism of higher education may restrict the development of students' ability to innovate. A proposed model for teaching innovation skills to professionals includes formal and continuing education.²⁸

Future skills such as digital ethics, tolerance of ambiguity, creativity, innovation competence, mission orientation, and change competence will be essential for innovation development. According to German professors of economics, law and social work, these skills are not yet widely taught.²⁹ Developing innovative capacity in the gifted requires a new approach to education, encompassing ten interrelated components such as problem-solving and risk-taking.⁴⁰ Renewing the commitment to gifted education is crucial for a more innovative society.³⁰ Establishing a system for identifying, selecting, and nurturing innovative talent is essential, as is creating an environment conducive to their growth.³¹

Gifted individuals can contribute to innovation through their unique creative potential, fostered through good educational matching and creative curriculum and teaching design.⁴ The three-ring concept of giftedness, which emphasizes creative/innovative productivity, can help identify and develop individuals capable of engaging in innovation.¹⁶ A new direction in gifted education, focusing on innovation education, is needed to develop innovators.¹⁷

The current school system does not recognise gifted students - on the contrary, they usually receive poor grades because, among other things, they are not challenged in class.^{32 33 34}

²⁴ World Economic Forum, "Future of Jobs Report – May 2023," Online Article (WEF, directed by Saadia Zahidi), 2023, <https://www.weforum.org/publications/the-future-of-jobs-report-2023/>, accessed April 2024.

²⁵ Kimble Byrd, "Creating Innovators: The Making of Young People Who Will Change the World," *Management Decision* 51.2 (2013): 453-454.

²⁶ W. I. L. M. A. Kotzé, "Die verpleegonderwyser—Dié innovateur?," *Curationis* 7.4 (1984): 7-9.

²⁷ Shi Ce, "Leader's Innovative Thinking and Innovation Ability," (2009).

²⁸ Yang Yong, "Theoretical Model Analysis of Innovating Ability Training," *Journal of Fuling Teachers College* (2004).

²⁹ Nina Horstmann, "Bildung für die Zukunft? Förderung von Future Skills in der Hochschullehre." *CHE Impulse* 13 (2023): 52 Seiten.

³⁰ Rena F. Subotnik, Paula Olszewski-Kubilius, and Frank C. Worrell, "Nurturing the young genius," *Scientific American Mind* 23.5 (2012): 50-57.

³¹ Sui Yanli, "Identification and Cultivation of Innovative Talents," *R & D Management* (2004).

³² Stanley Krippner, "Characteristics of Gifted and Talented Youth," *Maimonides Medical Center* (1967): 1-13.

How can we identify innovation potentials and document the effects of AI-supported formats?

In our study the relationship of innovation potential (X) and innovation achievement (Y) will be analysed, moderated by the context, and mediated by AI-Tools. **Figure 1** illustrates the relationships.

Figure 1 Variables of the empirical study in the context of complex problem solving.

The assessment of creative and cognitive potential in Germany is a complex and evolving field. The Test for Creative Thinking-Drawing Production (TCT-DP) has been used to measure creativity in German students, with some success in establishing measurement equivalence.³⁵ German education has been identified as a critical factor in developing students' creative potential.³⁶ The concept of creative potential and its relationship to talent has been explored, using psychological measures such as the EPoC and the Creative Profiler to assess creative potential in children and adults.³⁷ The relationship between personality traits, cognitive correlates, and creative performance has also been explored, with cognitive traits identified as key mediators.³⁸ Deshayes³⁹ extended this by identifying a model of cognitive functioning that includes working memory and analytical reasoning and also highlighted the role of resting brain functional connectivity, particularly in the attention network, in creative potential.

³³ Ann F. Isaacs, "The Annual Meeting of the National Association for Gifted Children Was Held Jointly With the American Personnel and Guidance Association in Cleveland, Ohio," *Gifted Child Quarterly* 3.2 (1959): 34-37.

³⁴ Poul Nissen, "Detecting talent from the perspectives of students, parents, and teachers," *US-China Education Review B* 9.4 (2019): 119-127.

³⁵ Caroline Theurer, Nicole E. Berner, and Frank Lipowsky, "Assessing creative potential as student outcome: On the applicability of the TCT-DP in repeated measures," *Thinking Skills and Creativity* 20 (2016): 74-82.

³⁶ Wu Chengyue, "German education and the development of students' creative potentialities," *Journal of Yunnan Normal University* (2001): n. pag.

³⁷ Todd Lubart, Franck Zenasni, and Baptiste Barbot, "Creative potential and its measurement," *International Journal for Talent Development and Creativity* 1.2 (2013): 41-51.

³⁸ Davide Piffer, "The personality and cognitive correlates of creative achievement," *Open Differential Psychology* (2014): 1-20.

³⁹ C. Deshayes, V. Paban, M. H. Ferrer, B. Alescio-Lautier, and C. Chambon, "A comprehensive approach to study the resting-state brain network related to creative potential," *Brain Structure and Function* 226.6 (2021): 1743-1753.

Innovation achievement is a multifaceted concept that encompasses a range of activities, from scientific and technological to financial and commercial.⁴⁰ The translation of scientific achievements into new products and services is a key aspect and a deliberate effort to bring about improvement.⁴¹ The successful exploitation of new ideas is also a critical factor.⁴²

Artificial intelligence (AI) tools have the potential to significantly enhance innovation achievement. Drewniak⁴³ and Brem⁴⁴ both highlight the role of AI in transforming innovation, with the former emphasizing the impact of learning and development tools on innovation potential and the latter introducing a conceptual framework for AI's role in innovation. Allam⁴⁵ and Fadziso⁴⁶ further explore the transformative potential of AI, with the former discussing its impact on the innovation process and the latter emphasizing its ability to increase efficiency and reshape innovation processes. Cockburn⁴⁷ and Kakatkar⁴⁸ both discuss the potential of AI in innovation analytics, with the former highlighting the shift towards application-oriented learning research and the latter presenting case studies of AI's role in driving innovation analytics. It can reshape the innovation process by improving predictive algorithms and the use of large data sets.⁵⁶ AI can also support scientific discovery and commercial innovation by improving lead prioritization and forecasting.⁴⁹

In addition to identifying potential through data, data can also support the transformation of potential into achievement. Individual and collaborative formats can help people to do this. Wendrich⁵⁰ emphasizes the role of metacognitive aspects, externalization, and representation in individual and collaborative interaction. Maysless⁵¹ highlights the benefits of group-based creativity skills training, which can

⁴⁰ A. Mehta, "What is Innovation: A Review," (2016).

⁴¹ Ronald V. White, "Innovation in Curriculum Planning and Program Development," *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics* 13 (1992): 244 - 259.

⁴² Edita Baranskaitė and Daiva Labanauskaitė, "The concept of innovation in the approach to novelty, value creating, interaction processes and social progress," *Regional Formation & Development Studies* 31(2) (2020): 50-58.

⁴³ Zbigniew Drewniak and Iwona Posadzińska, "Learning and Development Tools and the Innovative Potential of Artificial Intelligence Companies," *European Research Studies Journal* (2020): 288-404.

⁴⁴ Alexander Brem, Ferran Giones, and Marcel Werle "The AI Digital Revolution in Innovation: A Conceptual Framework of Artificial Intelligence Technologies for the Management of Innovation," *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* 70.2 (2021): 770-776.

⁴⁵ Sudhir Allam, "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Innovation - An Exploratory Analysis," *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts* 4.4 (2016): 810-814.

⁴⁶ Takudzwa Fadziso, "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Innovation," *Global Disclosure of Economics and Business* 7.2 (2018): 81-88.

⁴⁷ Iain M. Cockburn, Rebecca Henderson, and Scott Stern, "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Innovation: An Exploratory Analysis," In *The Economics of Artificial Intelligence: An Agenda*, eds. Ajay Agrawal, Joshua Gans, and Avi Goldfarb (University of Chicago Press, 2019), p. 115-146.

⁴⁸ Chinmay Kakatkar, Volker Bilgram, and Johann Füller, "Innovation analytics: Leveraging artificial intelligence in the innovation process," *Business Horizons* 63.2 (2020): 171-181.

⁴⁹ Ajay Agrawal, John McHale, and Alexander Oettl, "Artificial intelligence, scientific discovery, and commercial innovation," *Working Paper* (2019): 1-53.

⁵⁰ Robert E. Wendrich, "Collaborative Creativity: A Computational Approach: Raw Shaping Form Finding in Higher Education Domain," IEEE 13th International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies, Beijing, China, August 15-18, 2013, pp. 166-167.

⁵¹ Naama Maysless, Manish Saggur, Grace Hawthorne, and All Reiss, "Creativity in the twenty-first century: The added benefit of training and cooperation," In *Design Thinking Research: Making Distinctions: Collaboration versus Cooperation*, eds. Hasso Plattner, Christoph Meinel, and Larry Leifer (Springer Cham, 2018): 239-249.

improve perspective-taking, empathy, synthesis of ideas, and the development of improvisational skills. Sumadi⁵² also supports the effectiveness of collaborative learning in enhancing students' creativity. Brown⁵³ emphasizes the importance of tools that facilitate the collaborative process, allowing the suspension of judgment and the free flow of ideas. These findings suggest combining individual skill-building and collaborative learning, supported by appropriate tools, can significantly enhance cognitive and creative skills.

2 Approach and Methodology

Data collection approach

The study has four objectives and ten hypotheses:

- **Objective 1:** Capture insights from gifted adults and innovators on what they need to perform best in innovation contexts through a systematic literature review supported by AI tools^{4 18 23 34}, enriched with an empirical study aiming for 1.000 participants.
 - **Hypothesis 1:** Gifted learners need different formats than average gifted learners to transform innovation potential into innovation achievement.
 - **Hypothesis 2:** The context favouring innovators is similar for average and gifted learners.
- **Objective 2:** Capture the status quo of innovation potential at German schools and universities^{31 35 37 39 54} with a primary data collection study (basic population: 400,000 students; 260,000 high school graduates).
 - **Hypothesis 3:** 2% of high school graduates and first year students/workers have high innovation potential. Around 80% have medium innovation potential.
 - **Hypothesis 4:** 60% of all students turn their innovation potential into innovation performance.
- **Objective 3:** Understand how AI can best advise gifted and ordinary learners to unlock their innovation potential and transform their potential into innovation achievement^{43 44 45 46 47 48 49}
 - **Hypothesis 5:** AI improves the transformation of innovation potential into innovation achievement by 40%.
 - **Hypothesis 6:** AI improves the productivity of people in the innovation process by 60%.
 - **Hypothesis 7:** AI improves quality of innovation output by 30%.

⁵² Sumadi Sumadi, "Building Creativity through Collaborative Learning," *International Journal of Science and Research* 9 (2020): 1643-1636.

⁵³ John Seely Brown, "Enhancing creativity with collaborative tools," Proceedings of the 1986 ACM conference on Computer-supported cooperative work, Austin, Texas, December 3-5, 1986, pp. 368.

⁵⁴ K. Goff and E. P. Torrance, "Abbreviated Torrance Test for Adults (ATA) [Database record]," APA PsycTests (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1037/t12015-000>

- **Objective 4:** Understand which individual and collaborative formats lead to higher innovation achievement.^{12 50 51 52 53}
 - **Hypothesis 8:** Individual formats transform cognitive potential into innovation achievement.
 - **Hypothesis 9:** Collaborative formats transform creative potential into innovation achievement.
 - **Hypothesis 10:** Creative skills and analytical skills in combination are more likely to lead to innovation as if only one of the two skills are available.

Figure 2 aggregates the objectives and hypotheses of the empirical study.

1	Capture insights from gifted adults and innovators on what they need to perform best in innovation contexts through a systematic literature review supported by AI tools (Dai 2013, Fischer & Mazller 2014, Nissen 2019, Urban 1980), enriched with an empirical study aiming for 1.000 participants. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •H1: Gifted learners need different formats than average gifted learners to transform innovation potential into innovation achievement. •H2: The context favouring innovators is similar for average and gifted learners.
2	Capture the status quo of innovation potential at German schools and universities (Deshayes et al. 2021, Goff & Torrance 2019, Lubart et al. 2014, Theurer et al. 2016, Yanli 2004) with a primary data collection study (basic population: 400,000 students; 260,000 high school graduates). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •H3: 2% of high school graduates and first year students/workers have high innovation potential. Around 80% have medium innovation potential. •H4: 60% of all students turn their innovation potential into innovation performance.
3	Understand how AI can best advise gifted and ordinary learners to unlock their innovation potential and transform their potential into innovation achievement (Agrawal et al. 2019, Brem et al. 2021, Cockburg et l. 2018, Drewniak & Posadzinska 2020, Fadziso 2018, Kakatkaret et al. 2020, Sudhir 2016) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •H5: AI improves the transformation of innovation potential into innovation achievement by 40%. •H6: AI improves the productivity of people in the innovation process by 60%. •H7: AI improves quality of innovation output by 30%.
4	Understand which individual and collaborative formats lead to higher innovation achievement (Brown 1986, Maysless 2018, Rezulli 2003, Sumadi 2020, Wendrich 2013) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •H8: Individual formats transform cognitive potential into innovation achievement. •H9: Collaborative formats transform creative potential into innovation achievement. •H10: Creative skills and analytical skills in combination are more likely to lead to innovation as if only one of the two skills are available.

Figure 2 Objectives and Hypotheses of the Study.

Methodologies for the data analysis

The full survey uses an online instrument whose reliability, validity, and objectivity are pre-tested in a sample of 1.000 students and 1.000 high school graduates per age group. The quality of the resulting data set is a top priority, and it is prepared accordingly in collaboration with psychologists, computer scientists, learning analytics experts, and educationalists. The optimized online instrument will be the basis of a full German wide study with a basic population of 260.000 high school graduates⁵⁵ and 400.000 first year students⁵⁶.

The data sets are analysed with the software R using diverse multivariate analysis and machine learning packages. The interpretation is executed by an interdisciplinary consortium of economists, computer scientists, educationalists, and psychologists. Scientific validity, objectivity, and reliability indicators are also checked, and high standards are applied.

⁵⁵ Destatis, "Absolventen und Abgänger: Deutschland, Schuljahr, Geschlecht, Schulart, Schulabschlüsse," Online Table (Destatis), 2024, <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/genesis/online?language=de&sequenz=tabelleErgebnis&selectionname=21111-0004#abreadcrumb>, accessed April 2024.

⁵⁶ Destatis, "Studienanfänger: Bundesländer, Semester, Nationalität, Geschlecht," Online Table (Destatis), 2024, <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/genesis/online?sequenz=tabelleErgebnis&selectionname=21311-0014&zeitscheiben=1#abreadcrumb>, accessed April 2024.

Data collection and analysis are pseudonymized. The data is only stored once, and learners can view the data set and access it from the various institutions in real-time via a portal.

3 Interim Results

- The diagnostic test needs to take place in a silent environment without disruptions.
- The test needs to take place in a standardized and comparable environment.
- It needs to be clarified if an advisory test person is necessary.
- The data collection instrument should be fully online, not handwritten, and interactive.
- It remains to be experimentally investigated whether the independent selection of the test sequence by the test subjects has a positive effect on the test experience.
- All test content must be available free of charge and individually analysable. It is important to be able to completely control the data set and its evaluation.
- The results are to be output in real time with corresponding interpretation assistance.
- Test participants are given the opportunity to discuss the test results after receiving them.
- Video recording for recognising and analysing emotions won't be used.
- The analysis results are made available to all participants, for some of them with a time delay if they were drawn by computer in the experimental group "test person without knowledge of their potential".
- Care is taken to ensure that the test scenario is motivating and supportive so that all participants feel emotionally comfortable.
- All tests used must have a minimum level of reliability, validity and objectivity and be carried out by diagnosticians.

Table 1 summarises the findings for the following procedure based on the data collection and reflections with two diagnosticians.

Table 1 Interim findings for the upcoming empirical study

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Factor</i>	<i>Insight</i>
X: Innovation Potential	Creativity	Only tests that have a high degree of reliability, validity and objectivity and are intended for adults are used.
X: Innovation Potential	Cognition	Currently the HMT test is used, other analytical skills should be tested.
Y: Innovation Achievement	Performance	Behavioural indicators, such as creativity, risk-taking, and proactivity, could be used to assess innovation competence.
Y: Innovation Achievement	Product	Product quality could be measured using the design thinking criteria of desirability, feasibility, and future viability, supplemented by sustainability.
Y: Innovation Achievement	Process	Productivity along the complex problem-solving process could be measured using the formula result by time.
Mod: Context	Place	The context is determined by space, noise, climate, air, light, supervision, working climate.
Med: AI-Tool	AI-Tutor	AI-tools will be evaluated based on criteria (i.e., transparency, confidence level).

Source: Own representation.

4 Discussion and Outlook

Discussion

The need for innovation has increased in Germany. The existing education system is currently unable to meet the demands of the economy, and society.

Research studies indicate that psychologically established diagnostic tools can help to identify innovation potential. In addition, it is possible to measure innovation achievement with the help of competency tests. Behaviour or result data can capture or the productivity along the innovation process, or the quality of the results produced.

The planned study is intended to provide an overview of Germany's existing innovation potential and form the basis for the nationwide promotion of talented people so that they can develop innovations and contribute to social transformation. The study will also provide insights into commonly gifted people and provide them with a broad range of tools and formats to improve their performance in the innovation environment.

Outlook

In summer 2024, a new version of the questionnaire (very short Big5-version; Abbreviated TTCT for Adults, and HMT) will be tested with a group of ordinarily gifted and highly gifted school leavers - once as a quiz and once as a questionnaire. The results of the A-B-Experiment should provide information on whether playful elements can have an activating effect on participants and if quizzes are an option to scale.

In addition, a systematic literature analysis will be carried out to compare all innovation potential as well as innovation competence tests for adults regarding objectivity, reliability, and validity.

A data collection and analysis instrument will be developed in an interdisciplinary consortium, to identify the innovation potential and achievement just-in-time. A sample from a sufficiently large population will provide information on the need for optimisation and form the basis for a full survey.

As well, formats with AI Tools for innovation achievement enhancement will be designed, evaluated, and compared in the context of A/B experiments. An interdisciplinary group will decide on the setup for a long-term study embedded in companies and universities.

The author's vision is to establish a data-based human-machine relationship that aims to identify innovation potential early through dialogue and strengthen it according to the situation.

Feedback to the Author:

ⁱ The AI applications Grammarly, Copilot, Gemini, Perplexity, DeepL and Elicit were used for the realisation of this article.